

Indian Mutual Funds: Present State and Future Outlook
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ABSTRACT

India has been amongst the fastest growing markets for mutual funds since 2004, witnessing a CAGR of 29% percent in the five-year period from 2004 to 2008 as against the global average of 4 percent. As of August 2012, 44 asset management companies (AMCs) were operating in India with assets under management (AUM) of INR 6.4 trillion. Low customer awareness levels and financial literacy pose the biggest challenge to channelising household savings into mutual funds. Further, fund houses have shown limited focus on increasing retail penetration and building retail AUM. Most AMCs and distributors have a limited focus beyond the top 20 cities that is manifested in limited distribution channels and investor servicing. The Indian mutual fund industry has largely been product-led and not sufficiently customer focused with limited focus being accorded by players to innovation and development. There is limited flexibility in fees and pricing structures. Distributors and the mutual fund houses have exhibited limited interest in continuously engaging with customers post closure of sale as the commissions and incentives have been largely in the form of upfront fees from product sales. Limited focus of the public sector network including public sector banks, India Post and other similar organisations on distribution of mutual funds has also impeded the growth of the industry. Further multiple regulatory frameworks govern different verticals within the financial services sector, such as differential policies pertaining to the PAN card requirement, mode of payment, funds management by insurance companies and commission structures, among others. The present work reviews the current state of the Indian mutual fund industry and explores the outlook for the future.

Key Words: Mutual Funds, India, Current State, Future Outlook

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Objectives:

- a. The paper is intended to provide an overview of the present state of mutual funds and a future outlook vis a vis problems, preference, challenges and regulatory guidelines
- b. To provide suggestive plan for future growth of the industry

1.2 MUTUAL FUNDS: THE INDIAN SCENARIO

In India, the mutual fund industry Started with the setting up of Unit Trust of India (UTI) in 1964, enjoyed the monopoly power upto 1987. Public sector banks were allowed to establish mutual funds in 1987. Since 1993, Private sector and foreign institutions were permitted to set up Mutual Funds. By the end of March 2011 there are 41 fund houses, under 1131 schemes with managed assets of Rs 592250 Cr. This fast growing industry is regulated by the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI). Indian mutual Fund Industry is one of the fastest growing segments of the Indian economy. During last ten years period the industry has grown at nearly 22 percent CAGR.

1.2.1 AUM Growth

The Assets under Management (AUM) have grown at a rapid pace over the past few years, at a CAGR of 35 percent for the five-year period from 31 March 2005 to 31 March 2009. Over the 10-year period from 1999 to 2009 encompassing varied economic cycles, the industry grew at 22 percent CAGR. This growth was despite two falls in the AUM - the first being after the year 2001 due to the dotcom bubble burst, and the second in 2008 consequent to the global economic crisis (the first fall in AUM in March 2003 arising from the UTI split).

India has been amongst the fastest growing markets for mutual funds since 2004; in the five-year period from 2004 to 2008 (as of December) the Indian mutual fund industry grew at 29 % CAGR as against the global average of 4%. Over this period, the Mutual fund industry in mature markets like the US and France grew at 4 percent, while some of the emerging Markets viz. China and Brazil exceeded the growth witnessed in the Indian market. However, despite clocking growth rates that are Amongst the highest in the world, the Indian mutual Fund industry continues to be a very small market; Comprising 0.32% share of the global AUM of USD 18.97 trillion as of December 2008.

The equity markets remained flat during the quarter ending 30 June 2012, with the SENSEX delivering 0.14% and the Nifty losing -0.31% during the three months. The markets failed to keep up the momentum of the quarter ending 30 March 2012 when the BSE SENSEX rose 12.6%, while the Nifty advanced 14.5% during Jan-Mar 2012. In the fixed income market the yield on the managed by the 10 year GOI Benchmark remained flat. At the same time,

average assets managed by the mutual fund industry increased by 4.2% during the quarter. As per the data released by the Association of Mutual Funds in India (AMFI), the combined average AUM of the 44 fund houses increased to `692,704.92 crores during Apr-Jun 2012, up from `664,824.02 crores reported in Jan - March 2012. The highlight in June 2012 was the much awaited RBI mid quarter monetary policy review, with a consensus for a minimum 25 basis point cut in key lending rates. However, in retrospect forecasters agreed that another round of rate cuts after the 50 basis point cut in April 2012 was possibly wishful thinking. Instead the RBI, in order to improve the liquidity in the system and encourage banks to increase credit flow to the export sector, raised the limit of Export Credit Refinance (ECR) from 15% of outstanding export credit of banks to 50%, which is expected to pump in additional liquidity of over `300 billion.

1.2.2 Characteristics

The total number of fund house increased from 35 in FY 2000-01 to 41 in FY 2010-11 and had a CAGR of 1.59%. From FY 2002-03 to FY 2007-08 many fund houses were met with acquisitions and takeovers. The CAGR of schemes existing is 11.12% for 11 years period, there were 394 schemes operating under various categories in FY 2000-01 and gradually increased to 1131 schemes except in the financial years 2003-04(403 schemes) and 2009-10(882 schemes)

where there is a slight decline in the number of schemes compared to previous years. Total number of investor's folios shown a CAGR of 18.21% over 8 year's period from FY 2003-04 to 2010-11, in the FY 2004-05 there is a decline in the number of investors folios of 7,98,032 (-5.45%) and again in the FY 2010-11 9,41,658 (-1.95%) on account of huge redemptions made on equity schemes. Though there was a notable increase of 21.1% on debt schemes folios, a shrink of 18 lakhs folios on equity schemes to 3.9 Cr led to a fall in folios after six years compared to their previous year. The CAGR of total funds mobilized is 57.73%, and evidenced drastic increments year on year except in the year 2010-11 where there is a decline of Rs 11,59,507.25 (-11.57%) Total redemptions/repurchases had a CAGR of 59.46%. The inflows are high during the year 2008-08 and low during 2004-05, the FY 2008-09 and 2010-11 had outflows of Rs 28296.26 and Rs 49405.80 respectively and had wide fluctuations due to financial crisis and inflation. The CAGR of Total assets under management is 20.65% for the period of 2000-01 to 2010-11. There is a downtrend in AUM during the years 2002-03, 2008-09 and 2010-11 due to bifurcation in UTI in February 2003, Global financial crisis in 2008 and recession in 2011. By considering overall data except in few years, the performance of Indian Mutual fund Industry is good for the period of 11 years i.e. 2000-01 to 2010-11

The detailed review of sector wise number of funds in operation reveals that; Government (UTI) is alone up to FY 2002-03, Bank sponsored Joint venture Indian was 1 as on March 2005 through 2007 and 2 as on March 2008 through 2011, Bank sponsored Joint venture foreign was 1 from 2009-2011, Bank sponsored Joint venture others stood high in this category by having 6 fund houses gradually decreased to 1 by 2010 and increased to 2 by 2011. Institutional sponsored Mutual Funds were 4 in 2002 and decreased to 1 in 2003 and continuing till 2011. In the sector of Private sector mutual funds; Private sector Indian were 6 in the year

2001 and raised to 18 in 2011. Private sector foreign were 3 in 2008 and raised to 7 in 2011, private sector Joint venture Indian were 8 in 2001 and slowly declined to 4 by 2011 and private sector joint venture were 6 in 2011 having wide fluctuations in number due to mergers and acquisitions during the period. Considering the year 2011, the composition of Private sector Indian mutual funds were highest among all the sectors i.e. 43.9% followed by private sector foreign i.e. 17.07%. Private sector is playing a dominant role than other sectors. If we review the schemes under operation, they are showing bullish trend in all categories. Year on year the schemes are growing and recorded the CAGR of 11.12% in 11 years period, among different categories of schemes, Debt oriented schemes were highest in quantity followed by Growth/equity oriented schemes i.e. 328 in operation as on March 31st 2011. Fund houses are also introducing various innovative products to motivate the investors to invest in mutual funds. **Exhibit 2** shows the time line of introduction of various products. Considering the growth in number of folios in operation; Total folios in Open ended schemes of all categories in operation was 4,52,75,886, Close ended folios were 19,33,061 operating only in the category of Debt oriented, Growth/equity oriented and balanced schemes, Interval schemes folios were 24,315 operating under Debt oriented and Growth /equity oriented only as on March 31st 2011. Growth scheme folios followed by Income scheme folios are dominating among various categories

The Asset under Management (AUM) of IMFI is grown at a phenomenal rate from 1964-2011. If we look at the trend of AUM only twice the trend declined, i.e. the first bearish trend was in March 2003 because of bifurcation of UTI and second was in March 2009 because of world financial crises and a slight decline in 2011 due to recession in many economies. Apart from that we can say that the industry attained phase wise development and rapid growth after the entry of private sector mutual funds. The highest AUM is mobilized by Debt other than

assured returns category followed by equity others category. Being a new product exchange traded funds are grabbing the attention of investors because of hike in prices of gold and good performance of equity markets. Maximum growth was observed in AUM of Gold ETF's by 176.7%, equity exchange traded funds (ETFs) also witnessed higher growth of 162.90% during 2011.

1.2.3 AUM by Demography as on March, 2012

Besides low penetration, concentration of mutual funds to a few major cities has been another concern for the sector. Most AMC's and distributors have limited focus beyond the top 20 cities, as is evident from the limited distribution channels and limited investor servicing available beyond these cities. The top five cities contributed approximately 71.1 percent of the total AUM of the mutual fund sector, with Mumbai only accounting for about 42.1 percent in FY12. Lack of incentives for distributors to expand in small cities has resulted in mutual funds becoming an investment product in the hands of urban Indian industry.

Based on GDP and AUM as of 2011

1.2.4 Preference for Investment: Indian Households

Clearly, households seem to be quite risk averse, and prefer to invest in assets that are safe, familiar, and offer security of capital. Over a 20 year period when Indian capital markets have grown tremendously on many parameters, very few households have ventured too far beyond their bank, insurance agent, mandatory retirement funds and small savings. In fact, since 2000, household exposure to the capital market has crossed 7%

only once, in 2007-08.

How Indian households save and invest

Though investor population over the past decade has grown significantly, it hasn't quite enticed Indian households to follow suit. The participation by Indian households in the securities market continues to remain low.

Only 11% (24.5 million investors) of the households made investments in the securities market. It was also found that a chunk of the investors were urban Indians, what with 20% of the urban households invested in markets as against 6 per cent in rural India.

Mutual funds are the most preferred route for market investments, what with about 43 % of the respondents taking to it. Exposure to secondary market investments came in second, preferred by 22 % of the households. Nearly 15 % preferred bonds — probably owing to the instrument's steady returns promise vis-à-vis a volatile stock market. Initial public offerings garnered the interest of only 8.5 % households. The attraction for mutual funds was higher among rural households, what with 46 % of them choosing MF as against 41 % of urban investors.

Here again, villages close to urban centres significantly participated in financial markets, particularly in the mutual funds. An interesting sidelight here is that households with higher level of education tended to invest more. For instance, as against the 22% national average, about 26% of households with more than 15 years of education preferred to invest in secondary markets. It was also found that households with a higher level of education opted for a longer time horizon for their investments. As for IPO investing, preference was driven more by gender bias, as male investors were seen taking to it more than their female counterparts

1.3 Regulatory Framework

The Indian mutual fund industry in terms of regulatory framework is believed to match up to the most developed markets globally. The regulator, securities and exchange board of India (SEBI), has consistently introduced several regulatory measures and amendments aimed at protecting the interests of the small investor that augurs well for the long term growth of the industry. The implementation of prevention of money laundering (PMLA) rules. The latest

guidelines issued in December 2008, as part of the risk Management practices and procedures is expected to gain further momentum.

The regulatory and compliance ambit seeks to dwell on a range of issues Including the financial capability of the players to ensure resilience and Sustainability through increase in minimum net worth and capital Adequacy, investor protection and education through disclosure norms for more information to investors, distribution related regulations aimed at Introducing more transparency in the distribution system by reducing the information gap between investors and distributors, and by improving the Mechanism for distributor remuneration.

The success of the relatively nascent mutual fund industry in India, in its march forward, will be contingent on further evolving a robust regulatory and compliance framework that in supporting the growth needs of the industry ensures that only the fittest and the most prudent players survive.

1.4 Challenges and Issues

1.4.1 Problems related to structure

The problems related to structure under SEBI (Mutual Funds) Regulations,1996 are pertaining to regulations 2 (q), 7, 16 (5) , 24 (3) , 21 (b) , 24 (2) , 32, 33,43, & 44. AMFI has taken a lead & made representations to the SEBI & the Central Govt. to amend the regulations. The problems related to the Indian Trusts Act, 1882 are pertaining to individual/collective liability. The post – SEBI mutual funds have opted for trustee company structure. The liability of the trustees is more onerous under the board of trustees structure as compared to the trustee company structure. The Indian Trusts Act does not permit perpetual succession. The companies Act, 1956 permits perpetual succession but it can't protect the interest of the investors due to the privilege of limited liability.

The Govt. of India should consider enacting a separate comprehensive Mutual Funds Act and clearly spell out rights, duties and obligations of the various constituents of mutual fund to provide a uniform regulatory framework and to create a level playing field for all the mutual funds in the industry.

1.4.2. Problems related to the investors

The success of a mutual fund depends upon the confidence of the investors. UTI has established a marketing network of branches, chief representatives, collection centers and franchise offices through out the country. The marketing network of UTI is its unique strength as compared to

other mutual funds. UTI could mobilize Rs.75159 Cr. of investible funds through its 87 schemes due to its well established marketing network. All other mutual funds could not establish such a marketing network and can't compete with UTI in mobilizing public savings from rural and semi-urban areas. All the problems related to the investors are, lack of awareness and poor after sales service to the investors. The investors believed, so far , that the mutual funds promoted by UTI, LIC, and nationalized banks are guaranteed by the Central Govt. The majority of the new investors don't understand the concept, operations and advantages of investment in mutual funds before investing . Small businessmen, farmers and persons belonging to rural and semi-urban areas in low income group had no awareness about the mutual funds.

The queries received from the investors are promptly attended by all the private sector mutual funds. There are delays in attending queries by the transfer agents in case of UTI due to large number of queries received by them.

1.4.3. Problems related to working

The investible funds of the mutual funds increase when sales are more than the redemptions and decrease when the redemptions are more than sales creating the problems of maintaining liquidity. The investors prefer to invest in equity funds during boom period and shift their investments to debt funds during the recession period. The most profitable and high income & appreciation potential stocks during the boom period or at the time of investing funds in such stocks may become illiquid over a period of time .The investors can't take decisions of investment due to unavailability of track records of working. HDFC and Standard Chartered Mutual Funds started their operations in 2000, all other mutual funds except UTI have the track record of 3 to 5 years. Unless the track records of working of mutual funds is available covering the several stock market booms and crashes, the investors can't judge which schemes or mutual funds are better alternatives for investments. There are several problems related to UTI such as non-disclosure of portfolio, inter scheme transfer of funds, lack of professional fund managers, sale & repurchase of units of US-64 at prices not related to its NAV, bureaucratic working, etc. AMFI has constituted committees on valuation, best practices and credit policy and working groups on valuation of gilt-securities, standardization of disclosure, pensions, etc. to ensure uniform working and disclosure practices.

1.4.4. Problems related to performance

The investor prefers safety of the principal amount, regular returns, long-term growth, income tax benefits, etc. The mutual fund schemes have been designed based on the preferences of the investors, changes in stock/capital market, returns on various instruments and changing profile of the investors. The schemes are framed and conceptualized by the top management of the mutual funds and marketed by their branches and through the agents. The agents and the sales executives of the mutual funds assure higher returns to the investors and paint a rosy picture about the mutual funds while marketing schemes. The mutual funds in our country have been quite wrongly promoted as an alternative to equity investing and created very high expectations in the minds of the investors. The ignorance of the investors about mutual funds coupled with aggressive selling by promising higher returns to the investors have resulted into loss of investors' confidence due to inability to provide higher returns. All mutual funds set a higher target for mobilization of savings from the investor by launching new schemes and expanding investor base. The agents or distributor of mutual funds are more governed by commissions and incentives they get for selling the schemes and not by the requirements of the investors and quality of the products. They share commissions with the investors and don't explain the risk factors to them. The investors who invest in growth or equity schemes consider it as an alternative to stock market investing and the investors who invest in debt schemes expect higher returns on their investments than returns on nationalized banks' fixed deposits. The investors expect higher returns and get dissatisfied when they don't receive the expected returns. The NAV of the mutual fund scheme gets discounted on debiting the front-ended load of issue expenses after closure, further discounted on listing and continue to decline on trading due to poor demand for such units due to the poor sentiments of the investors. The mutual funds are bound to invest the funds as per their investment objectives of each scheme published in the offer document. After the issue is over, it becomes the mandate and the mutual funds have no choice to invest the funds in other securities, which can provide higher returns. The greater transparency, increased innovations, better services to the investors, liquidity and higher returns will make mutual fund schemes more popular and investors friendly.

There are many Challenges Facing Mutual Funds which is of prime concern to the people who have an investment spree. People find mutual fund investment so much interesting because they think they can gain high rate of return by diversifying their investment and risk. But, in reality

this scope of high rate of returns is just one side of the coin. On the other side, there is the harsh reality of highly Fluctuating Rate of Returns. Though there are other disadvantages also, this concern of fluctuating returns is most possibly the greatest challenge faced by the mutual fund.

In spite of being a diversified investment solution, mutual funds investment in no way guarantees any return. If the market prices of major shares and bonds fall, then the value of mutual fund shares are sure to go down, no matter how diversified the mutual fund portfolio be. It can be said that mutual fund investment is somewhat lower risky than Direct Investment in stocks. But, every time a person invests in mutual fund, he unavoidably carries the risk of losing money.

1.4.5 The Other Challenges

Diversification or Over Diversification- In order to diversify the investment, many times the mutual fund companies get involved in Over Diversification. The risk of holding a single financial security is removed by diversification. But, in case of over diversification, investors diversify so much that many time they end up with investing in funds that are highly related and thus the benefit of risk diversification is ruled out.. **Taxes-**Every year, most of the mutual funds sell substantial amount of their holdings. If they earn profit by this sell, then the investors receive the Profit Income. For most of the mutual funds, the investors are bound to pay taxes on these incomes, even if they reinvest the income. **Costs-** Most of the mutual funds charge Shareholder Fees and Fund Operating Fees from the investors. In the year, in which mutual fund fails to make profit and the investors get no return, these fees only blow up the losses.

1.4.6 Effect of SEBI Guidelines

Until a few years ago, mutual funds thrived on the salesmanship of independent distributors who canvassed investors for a commission, which was paid by the funds from an entry fee charged to new investors. In 2009, SEBI banned such entry loads, thus significantly curbing the funds' ability to pay huge commissions and take agents on lavish foreign trips.

This, in turn, affected sales. Listless stock markets did not help either, and the funds kept badgering SEBI for a change in rules, maintaining that its shackles were slowly choking the industry. The new SEBI guidelines bring the broker back into the game, but also aim to force them to evolve from being mere product pushers to financial advisors.

The new guidelines are supposed to give incentives to distributors to sell mutual funds outside the top 15 cities. Mutual funds will be able to charge a fee (known as an expense ratio) of up to

0.3 % point more for expenses on the investment flows from small cities and towns. The extra cash can go to distributors who help canvas investors from such uncharted territories.

The new guidelines allow funds with a corpus of less than ` 100 crore to charge 3% of the corpus for expenses, up from the earlier 2.5 percent.

Bajaj Capital is the 12th largest distributor of mutual funds, at ` . 36 crore, based on FY2012 (financial year 2011-12) data from the Association of Mutual Funds in India (AMFI).

To encourage mutual funds to directly approach investors, SEBI has created two plans: A direct plan that will have a higher net asset value, and a distributor plan that will have a net asset value lower by about 0.5 percentage point to accommodate commissions.

This means mutual funds will be selling their funds through brokers, while also competing with them for investors. Many distributors feel they will be increasingly marginalised as investors will eventually shift to the direct plan. Some distributors are thinking of an advisory model, where they will guide investors to the direct plan for a fee. But the large majority of distributors do not agree, and mutual funds also support their view.

Investors do not pay advisory for FDs, insurances or any other financial product. Why will they pay fees to mutual fund distributors? The advisory model is a dream that will take a long time to become successful in a country like India, In India, there are 44 asset management companies (AMCs) managing up to Rs 7.68 lakh crore. The top five managers account for around 54 percent of total assets. The smaller AMCs feel that the SEBI guidelines are getting the distributor back into the game but only for the big funds, which have saturated the big cities. These are the funds that can afford to pay high commissions to brokers and, at the same time, are setting up their own teams in smaller towns.

1.4.7 Voice of the Customer

The Endeavour of mutual fund investments is to leverage professional and prudent fund management techniques and thereby maximise returns for the investors while minimising risk. While mutual funds are often the preferred avenue for investment over direct investments into the capital markets by risk averse investors, customers have had widely varying experiences with purchase of mutual funds. Thus, it is critical for the industry to understand the perspectives of Indian investors so as to use their inputs to further enhance the customer experience with mutual funds.

1.3.8 Reasons offered by investors for not investing in mutual funds

Availability of a large number of mutual funds schemes makes investment decision complex and difficult

Complicated KYC norms restrict potential investors

Banks and IFAs remain the preferred channel given that investors trust them for their advice and after sales service.

Channels preferred by investors for investing in mutual funds

Guidance for selection of Mutual Funds

1.5 Motivating factors for investing in mutual funds

Investment in Mutual Funds is attractive to customers owing to tax benefits

- Consistency in fund performance and brand equity influence customers to make relevant selection of mutual fund schemes
- Simplification of Processes to Increase the Quantum of Investments

1.5.1 Investors expectations

Mutual fund products

- Protective products with guaranteed income and good absolute returns.
- Retired persons, want more debt funds options with a safe mechanism of regular saving along

with the varied pension options.

- Assured returns schemes that are a mix of risk-free and high-risk portfolio to invest small sums of money.
- A clear and easy explanation of various schemes.

1.5.2 Funds Management

- Wish to listen to fund managers' views on outlook for various sectors, industry performance, fund performance, etc. but have never been invited by any fund house for this.
- AMCs should not depend on the Fund Manager but its process for the success of their products.

1.5.3 Investor Servicing

- Easy access to the Fund House for direct subscription since I do not want to pay entry load.
- Better service from the fund house in terms of NAV updates through weekly SMS alerts to know the value of the investments.
- All the services at the door step - right from getting help in filling in the application form to depositing a cheque.
- Interact with more knowledgeable people at the call centers to attend to our complaints from a technical perspective, and not just to handle routine operational level problems.
- AMCs should send a report on the investment status and performance on a regular basis
- Agents commission should be linked to investor satisfaction and attractiveness of the fund suggested, which should be payable in phases, depending upon the success of the advice
- Reduce and simplify the documentation required and the processes involved to understand the purpose for which this will be used.

1.5.4 Investment Advice

- Since own investment decisions without relying on anyone's advice are made, a single platform for transacting and performance monitoring, to track my investments across various AMCs.
- Objective advice that's best suited to the needs and which is not driven by commissions received by my advisor.
- As long as the fund house pays the commission to the advisor, there is always a conflict. unbiased advice cannot be provided if they are paid by the fund house for the advice. This ensures that the advisor is acting in the favor of the fund house and is not driven by my interests and needs of the investor.

1.5.5 Regulator Intervention

- Can SEBI provide Certification of Fund managers, to assure me of high quality management of my funds?
- SEBI should provide a list of registered distributors on their website since to know if my advisor is certified and qualified to advise me.
- Can SEBI put in place a mechanism through which one can rely upon the advice provided by the Mutual Fund agent?

1.5.6 Tax Benefits

- Why to pay Securities Transaction Tax?
- Why should long-term capital gain tax on my debt funds be paid when it is not required to pay this on equity funds?
- The Government must provide a favorable tax regime for Fund of Funds that implies extending tax benefits to investors and also to the funds.
- The Government must provide tax sops to encourage investment in equity (including overseas equity) as a long term saving and to encourage investments in the infrastructure sector (debt as well as equity); tax sops should also be extended to schemes investing in these areas as well.

2. Expected Drivers For Future Growth, expected Industry Growth Projections And Overall Future Outlook Across Various Dimensions – Customers, Markets, Products, Distribution Channels And Regulatory Frameworks.

2.1 Growth Drivers

Although several macroeconomic and demographic factors affect the growth of the industry, the key underlying driver for all the categories of funds is the key economic indicator – the GDP growth rate. The growth drivers for customer segments have been listed in the table below along with the expected impact of each on the AUM.

Key Growth Drivers	Expected Impact
	Retail Segment
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rising disposable incomes and savings • Favourable demographics such as increasing proportion of working population (20-59 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in disposable incomes and household financial savings may result in households seeking alternate avenues for investments to yield higher returns with reasonable risk • Favourable demographics like urbanisation and a relatively young population having an increased risk

<p>years) and increasing urbanisation resulting in increased levels of financial savviness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Innovations in distribution Increased awareness levels Quality financial planning 	<p>appetite, are likely to save more and seek to invest a higher proportion of those savings in market-linked instruments such as mutual funds</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Distribution innovations are expected to increased mutual fund penetration specifically in Tier 2 and Tier 3 towns thereby expanding the mutual fund customer base Improved awareness levels and enhanced financial literacy is expected to aid the understanding of mutual fund products Appropriate asset allocation and potential for wealth creation
Institutional Segment	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rising corporate earnings Maturing capital markets Interest rate cycle Call money market rates Corporate debt and commercial Papers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased demand for sophisticated treasury management products A better economic situation in the country is likely to ensure a steady fall in the interest rates

3. Future Outlook

Industry AUM is likely to continue to grow in the range of 15 to 25% from the period 2010 to 2015.

Scenario 1: In the event of a quick economic revival and positive reinforcement of growth drivers identified. The Indian mutual fund industry may grow at the rate of 22-25 percent in the period from 2010 to 2015, resulting in AUM of INR 16,000 to 18,000 billion in 2015.

Key growth drivers for this scenario include:

- Increased retail investor participation with a preference for mutual funds over other asset classes perceived to be more risky. This could result in the fulfilment of growing financial aspirations, enabled by rising disposable incomes and increased financial savings
- Innovations in distribution driven by increase in the number of certified IFAs and banks selling mutual funds focusing on Tier 2 and Tier 3 towns
- Increase in institutional participation triggered by rising corporate revenues with increased economic activity.

Scenario 2: In the event of a relatively slower economic revival resulting in the identified growth drivers not reaching their full potential, KPMG in India is of the view that the Indian mutual fund industry may grow in the range of 15-18 percent in the period from 2010 to 2015, resulting in AUM of INR 15,000 to 17,000 billion in 2015.

Key factors driving the growth in spite of the slow revival of the economy include:

- Incremental increase in retail investor participation owing to limited focus beyond Tier 2 towns and limited efforts to draw risk averse customers of traditional products under the fold of mutual funds
- Tightening of liquidity leading to better yields on instruments liquid funds invest in, thereby driving investments from the institutional investors.

Further.

- Industry profitability may reduce further as revenues shrink and operating costs escalate
- Product innovation is expected to be limited
- Market deepening and widening is expected with the objective of increased retail penetration and participation in mutual funds
- Massive expansion is expected in the mutual fund distribution network
- The regulatory and compliance framework for mutual funds is likely to get aligned with the frameworks across the financial services spectrum

To summarise, the Indian mutual fund industry is expected to witness rapid growth in AUM over the next few years. The industry, however, faces the challenge of achieving sustained profitable growth while increasing retail penetration and expanding the reach of mutual funds into rural areas.

4. Suggestive Plans for Transformational Growth

The key industry stakeholders are of the view that opportunities exist for surpassing the growth potential of the Indian mutual fund industry and making the industry more profitable through a collaborative effort across all the key stakeholders to reach out to the customer, viz. AMCs, distribution channel partners, service providers such as R&T Agents, custodians and fund accountants, CII, AMFI, the regulator SEBI and the media, among others.

4.1 Key initiatives that are required to be undertaken for the Indian mutual fund industry to grow and effectively compete in a dynamic environment.

- Massive Increase in Mutual Fund Penetration Through Customer Awareness Campaigns

Given that customer awareness is the pre-requisite for the achievement of the industry growth potential, there is a need for planning, financing and executing initiatives aimed at increasing financial literacy and enhancing investor education across the entire country through a sustained collaborative effort across all stakeholders. Financing a Sustainable Nationwide Customer Awareness Program. Creation of the ‘Mutual Fund Education Fund’ – a common corpus of funds from AMCs and distributors through mandatory levy on the investment management fee earned by AMCs and on the commissions earned by distributors from mutual fund sales. This Fund should be suitably ring-fenced and managed/ administered by the industry association.

- Conducting a Nationwide Customer Awareness Program
- Promoting Financial Planning Awareness in Educational Institutions
- The objective of product innovation by AMCs should be driven by the need to introduce simple products to attract and retain risk averse and first time investors to start investing in mutual funds.

- Introduction of Customer-Friendly Products and Product Features: Pricing innovations should focus on distributor compensation and administration.
- Pricing Flexibility : Pricing innovations should focus on distributor compensation and administration
- Public Sector Thrust into Mutual Funds Distribution and Focus on Strengthening presence beyond Tier 2 Cities.
- Focus on Increasing Customer Engagement Pre and Post Completion of the Investment
- Strengthening of Associations viz. AMFI
- Development of a Common Online Platform: AMFI to coordinate the roll out of a common online platform for AMCs which will result in increasing reach, reducing distribution costs and making transactions free from operational issues.
- Facilitating Distributor Education and Mandatory Certification
- Building an Industry Data Repository
- Creation of a SEBI recognised association of distributors of mutual fund products with a clearly defined charter and role.
- Constitution of a Steering Committee of Financial Services Regulators under the Ministry of Finance.
- Areas Requiring Harmonisation Outsourcing of funds management by insurance companies to AMCs independent of the assets under management, by removing the threshold of INR 80 billion which exists currently • Allow PSUs to invest larger surpluses in mutual funds and open up investment in private sector and foreign mutual funds.
- Acceptance and Rollout of the Unique Identification Card: Implementation of the Unique Identification Card as a valid document for KYC. The Government has announced that a Unique Identification Card would be issued to all Citizens. This should be implemented and the card should be a valid document for KYC.

5. CONCLUSION

There is a perceived need to review risk and performance analysis capabilities and

governance structures, to meet fiduciary responsibilities and the increasing demand for transparency. AMCs therefore need to re-orient their business towards fulfilling customer needs. As customers seek trusted advisors, the manufacturer-distributor-customer relationship is expected to be centered not on the sale of products, but for collectively promoting the financial success of customers across all facets of their professional and personal lives which would require creating a collaborative network of experts in funds management and financial advice, innovative product offerings, efficient service delivery and supporting technology. The mutual fund industry today needs to develop products to fulfill customer needs and help customers understand how its products cater to their needs.

Given that the industry needs to collectively work towards riding over the dynamic and relatively less favorable environment at present, the next phase for the industry is likely to be characterised by a stronger focus on customer centricity. Other areas of focus are likely to be cost management and enabling strong governance and regulatory framework – all aimed at helping the industry achieve sustained, profitable growth.

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